

National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

Lailatul Selfi Anggreni, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS) with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS) " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS) based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that there are 8 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS). The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS), both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS); Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

The National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS) is an institution responsible for resolving various disputes in the field of Islamic economics that have not been fully resolved due to limited human and financial resources. The scope of BASYARNAS is focused on the field of arbitration and is usually limited to sharia banking, but in the future it will be expanded to the service and industrial sectors, so that BASYARNAS can make an important contribution to society (Sanawiah, 2013).

BASYARNAS has the main responsibility for resolving sharia banking disputes by complying with the procedural procedures at BASYARNAS and existing laws and regulations and legal sources (Sakti M, Yuli Y, Faculty of W at al., 2017). Settlement of banking disputes through out-of-court channels can be carried out through BASYARNAS with settlement procedures that occur between Sharia Banks and Syariah Bank customers who experience problems. This process begins with an arbitration clause that is registered with the arbitration secretary through BASYARNAS in accordance with Law no. 30 of 1999 (Sulistiyowati, 2014)

There have been many publications regarding the discussion of the BASYARNAS decision. Scientific publications about BASYARNAS on the Digital

Reference Guard (GARUDA) website in 2013-2022 amounted to 67 journals. Research regarding BASYARNAS is really needed on dispute issues that occur, so as to provide decisions that are fair and in accordance with Islamic law.

Puspita (2017) stated that interest in dispute resolution through BASYARNAS began to increase since the promulgation of Law no. 30 of 1999. This development is in line with the flow of globalization, so research results state that arbitration is an option for entrepreneurs or banks in resolving disputes. Because, compared to dispute resolution through court, arbitration is more efficient, fast and complete. This is due to the absence of causes and appeals, so the decision is final and has permanent legal force. Apart from that, there are other advantages, namely the confidentiality of the trial and the non-publication of the arbitration award.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS) using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS), so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS), both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

The National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS) changed its name to the Indonesian Muamalat Arbitration Board (BAMUI), one of the first Islamic arbitration institutions established in Indonesia. BASYARNAS is the only institution in Indonesia that handles muamalah disputes in the fields of trade, finance, industry, services and other sectors (MUI Decree No. Kep-09/MUI/XII/2013, 24 December 2003). BASYARNAS is based on Supreme Court Regulation (PERMA) No. 14 of 2016 concerning Sharia Economic Case Procedures (Faizal, 2021).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such

as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Basyarnas " and "Sharia Arbitration" for the entire year period (2013 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS)

The results of the search for scientific journal publications about BASYARNAS in Sharia Financial Institutions for 9 years, namely from 2013 to 2022, show growth in journal publications every year, especially in the last 4 years. The articles obtained were 67 titles from accredited national and international journals. In 2019 there were 19 journals published. Therefore, 10 articles about BASYARNAS should be published every year.

Tab el 1. Scientific Publication Data About BASYARNAS Based on Year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2013	2	2018	8
2014	4	2019	13
2015	3	2020	8
2016	5	2021	9
2017	7	2022	7
Number of Publication Articles 66			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 3 affiliates/institutions that most frequently publish articles about BASYARNAS. The Journal of Sharia Economic Law is the journal that most frequently publishes articles about BASYARNAS, namely 3 articles.

Tab el 2. Institutional Data and Journal Article Publisher BASYARNAS

Name of Institution/Affiliation	Publication Journal
Journal of Sharia Economic Law	3
Journal of Legal Sciences and Humanities, Journal of Islamic Economic Law, Indonesian Journal of Law and Islamic Law, International Journal of Nusantara Islam, Journal of Law.	2
USM Law Review Journal, Journal of Civil Procedure Law, Journal of Non-formal Education Science, Journal of Sharia and Legal Sciences, Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Journal of Islamic Law Studies, Ash Syari'ah, Muamalah Study Program Scientific Journal, Islamic Education Journal, Journal of Religious Studies, IJLIL, Indonesian Journal of Religion and Society, Journal of Scientific Economics, Journal of Islamic Studies, JOEMS (Journal of Education and Management Studies), Jornal of Judicial Review, Aghniya Journal, Asas Journal, Journal of Sharia Economics, Accounting and Banking, Journal of Progressive Law.	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that all researchers have only published an article once.

Table 1. Researchers around BASYARNAS

Researcher	Institution
Eeng Juli Efrianto, Ahmad Faizun	UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta
Nurul Irfan, Afwan Faizin, Bukhori Muslim	UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta
Muhibuthabary	UIN Ar-Raniry Aceh
Sofian Al Hakim, Muhammad Hasanuddin	UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung
Zaidah Nur Rosidah, Layyin Mahfiana	IAIN Surakarta
Bhismoadi Tri Wahyu Faizal, Masyithah, Nurul Fitriyah, Riqqa Soviana, Ulfa Hasanah	IAIN Madura
Heris Suhendar, Karimatul Khasanah	IAIN Pekalongan
Sulistiyowati	IAIN Kediri
Habibi	IAIN Padangsidempuan
Fauzan	IAIN Bengkulu
Usammah	IAIN Lhokseumawe
Shams Eliaz Bahri	IAIN Batusangkar
Dewi Nurul Musjtari, Riki Ali Nurdin, Dewi Nurul Musjtari, Fadia Fitriyanti, Ani Yunita, Muhammad Khaeruddin Hamsin, Ani Yunita	Yogyakarta Muhammadiyah University
Ahmad Nurozi	Indonesian Islamic University Yogyakarta
Andria Luhur Prakoso	muhammadiyah Surakarta university
Muhammad Arifin	Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra Medan
Eko Priadi, Mhd. Erwin Munthe	STIE Syariah Bengkalis
Fadzila Ulfa Nadia	Janabadra University
Afifatul Bariroh, Kholis Firmansyah, Mustamim	Kh University Wahab Hasbullah
Muthia Sakti, Yuliana Yuli W	UPN Veteran Jakarta
Ridzky Adityanto	Lambung Mangkurat University
Anton Minardi	Pasundan University
Jamaluddin	Pamulang University
Muslih, Abdur Rohman Husen, Nunung Radliyah	Lampung University
Dhaniar Eka Budiastanti, Istislam, Bambang Winarno, Irham Rahman, Umm Hilmy, Siti Hamidah	Brawijaya University
Neni Sri Imaniyati, Neneng Nurhasanah, Panji Adam	Airlangga University
Ro'fah Setyowat	Diponegoro University
Ephin Apriyandanu	Semarang University
Muhamad Rian Mardiansyah, Devi Siti Hamzah Marpaung, Tiyas Amelina, Nadila Septyani Putriagustin	Singaperbangsa Karawang University
Tri Novianti, Ricky Fadila	Riau Islands University
Amanda Tikha Santriyati	Nahdlatul Ulama Madiun Islamic College

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 33 topics, namely: alternative dispute resolution, arbitration, arbitration clause, bamui, board, burden, business, business person, business world, content, contract, cost, decree, dispute, existence, fatwa, institution, judiciary, jurisdiction, legal basis, mudharabah contract, national arbitration, paper, peace, positive law, provision, referee judge, role, settlement, sharia, sharia arbitration, trade, way.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 24 topics, namely: arbitration, sharia arbitration, national sharia arbitration body, basyarnas, basyarnas decision, can be used as a legal choice for the parties, legal basis, ijma, judicial power, regarding, articles, dispute resolution, Basyarnas procedural regulations, sharia principles, procedures, rules, sharia business disputes, SK MUI, state court, about arbitration and, about sharia banking, law number, uu no, uu number.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 19 topics, namely: absolute authority, arbitrator, arbitrator, bankruptcy, basyarnas diy, basyarnas diy region, case, dispute resolution, dispute settlement, field, increase, Islamic economic dispute, national sharia arbitration board, settlement sharia economic dispute, principle, religious courts, resolution, sharia economic dispute, substance.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 17 topics, namely: ability, agreement, arbitration agreement, basic policy, implementation, Islamic banking dispute, Islamic law, law number, legal aid, library research, meaning, national legal system, perspective, regulation, sharia banking dispute, sharium, about aid law through sharia arbitration in resolving sharia banking disputes.
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 15 topics, namely: analysis, arbitration, arbitration clause, authority, court, judge, contains arbitration clauses, religious courts, religious courts in adjudicating, religious courts, economic sharia, economic conflict sharia, statute approach, sharia.
- Cluster 6. Black consists of 14 topics, namely: addition, cancellation, decision, development, district court, enactment, execution, law no, legal certainty, legal uncertainty, non litigation, research method, sharia arbitration award, sharia economy.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 14 topics, namely: agree, answer, application, basis, basyarnas, consideration, customer, Islamic principle, literature study, national sharia arbitration agency, research problem, sharia economic dispute resolution, sharia principle, tern.
- Cluster 8. Brown color consists of 5 topics, namely: bank Indonesia sharia, bank Indonesia sharia certificate, gdp, inflation, study.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 8 topics related to the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS), namely:

First, dispute resolution is simple, low cost, fair, fast, and in accordance with sharia principles. Dispute resolution through ADR consists of several methods, including consultation, negotiation, mediation, conciliation, or expert assessment. In resolving disputes through ADR, disputing parties can reach an

agreement peacefully without having to go through a court process which takes more time and costs. Therefore, dispute resolution through ADR can be a good alternative for parties who want to resolve disputes simply, with low costs, fairly, quickly, and in accordance with sharia principles at the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS).

Second, dispute resolution in sharia banking (based on Law No. 30 of 1999, the execution of mortgage rights, and the limits of authority with religious courts), sharia economics (reviewed from the principles of legal certainty, justice and benefit), sharia business, Murabahah contracts (among sharia banking and certain companies), Musyarakah contracts, and waqf.

Third, the annulment of the Basyarnas decision based on Law no. 3 of 2006. In the event of an annulment of the BASYARNAS decision, the party who feels aggrieved can submit a request for an annulment of the decision to the Religious Court. The Religious Court will examine the application and decide whether the BASYARNAS decision can be annulled or not.

Fourth, Basyarnas' position is based on MK decision no. 93/Puu-X/2012, MUI fatwa, and national law.

Fifth, the role of Basyarnas in handling sharia banking bankruptcy based on Law no. 21 of 2008. BASYARNAS has a role in handling sharia banking bankruptcy as an alternative resolution of sharia banking disputes. BASYARNAS can resolve sharia banking bankruptcy disputes by means of mediation or arbitration and provide recommendations to the court to resolve sharia banking bankruptcy disputes.

Sixth, increasing the quality of competence and challenges of sharia arbitrators. The importance of considering the expertise possessed by human resources when recruiting or selecting processes greatly influences their performance. In the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS), the board of arbitrators has a combination of competencies, both from the disciplines of law, sharia economics, Islamic law, and some are scientists in the field of engagement and agreement law.

Seventh, dealing with street vendors who fail to pay in financing using the Rahn contract.

Eighth, third party resistance (derden verzet).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 8 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding the National Sharia Arbitration Board (BASYARNAS).

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada

- Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar*

quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>

- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni*, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>